

Original Article

Content Analysis of 9th Grade Pakistan Studies Curriculum for Social Cohesion

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Abstract

The study focuses on the role of the 9th grade Pakistan Studies curriculum in ensuring social cohesion. The study, through qualitative content analysis, considers textbooks content on the basis of five parameters namely; (A) common values and respect to people and institutions, (B) law and stable society, (C) cohesion and lessening of disparity, (D) trust and collaboration among communities, and (E) feeling of national identification and pride. The results show that although the curriculum has a particular focus on national identity and concertedness, it does not embody vital aspects, like diversity and intergroup relationship. Suggestions are given: to update the curriculum by focusing on inclusion and respect to each other.

Keywords: Social Cohesion, Curriculum Analysis, Pakistan Studies, Diversity, National Identity

Introduction

Education means a lot in building up the ideological, cultural and social values of any given society. The education system in Pakistani, should not only be regarded as an instrument of educating the people, it should be viewed also as a pivotal platform in gaining conformity, democratic values and civic consciousness in multicultural and multi-ethnic states of the world like Pakistan and others. Providing the students with the inclusive and the pluralistic set of perceptions is one of the most important roles of the curriculum design, particularly in the society where trends such as ethnic and language, religious, and socio-economic diversity are characteristic.

Social cohesion is the ability of a society to guarantee the wellbeing of all of its members by reducing the existence of inequalities and marginalizing people. Chan et al. (2006) postulate that, social cohesion is based on value, mutual respect, feeling of belonging and participation opportunities. It has now emerged as a national development preminent issue especially in post-colonial and conflict ridden nations. The system of education, particularly the school curriculum, especially in this kind of setting would become a very strong tool of unifying different communities and encouraging peaceful co-existence.

The school curriculum, and in particular some subjects dealing with Pakistan Studies, has been traditionally employed as the agent involved in nation building in Pakistan. Though we have been told that this was done with an idea of generating one national identity, opponents believe that it is usually at the cost of diversity, inclusiveness and critical thinking (Nayyar & Salim, 2003). National policies of Pakistan and its Constitution acknowledge the values of unity and equality but it is also a question of academic research to what extent these values have been transferred into the curriculum itself.

As one of the most taught documents due to its ideological sensitivity, the 9th -grade Pakistan Studies textbook is a critical initial point through which one can study the interconnection of curriculum and social cohesion. With students at this age group starting to explore issues that are civic and national, the interpretations adopted at a given textbook, will greatly affect how students learn to know their identity, citizenship and community.

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This paper acts as a qualitative study and explores the extent to which social cohesion is reflected in the curriculum of Pakistan Studies as offered at 9th grade at the school. It employs a content analysis model grounded on five parameters, (A) shared values and respect institutions (B) law and social order (C) equity and unity across groups (D) trust and cooperation within communities (E) territorial belonging and national identity.

Statement of the Problem

The aim of the curriculum (Pakistan Studies) at ninth grade is to make the pupils learn about the history, values, and culture of the country. It has not been analyzed critically but how effectively has this curriculum served to enhance social cohesion, which is the ability to foster harmony, respect and understanding among pupils of diverse backgrounds. It should be noted that what is the suitable curriculum towards what different religious, national and cultural groups and whether the curriculum propagates the principles that would let to unity in society considering the diverse population in Pakistan. This study seeks to bridge this gap since by using a content analysis of the textbooks used in Pakistan Studies, it will be evaluating the capacity of the textbooks to inculcate social cohesion and identify areas that need improvement.

Objectives of the Study

1. To identify how the Constitution of Pakistan facilitates social cohesion among diverse groups.
2. To analyze the inclusion of social cohesion elements in national education policies.
3. To evaluate the 9th-grade Pakistan Studies curriculum for its effectiveness in promoting social cohesion.

Research Questions

1. How does the Constitution of Pakistan facilitate social cohesion among its diverse ethnic and religious groups?
2. How do recent national education policies in Pakistan address and promote social cohesion?
3. How does the 9th-grade federal board Pakistan Studies curriculum foster social cohesion among students?

Literature Review

Theory of Multicultural Education and Social Cohesion

The foundation of dealing with the perspective of how curriculum can advance social cohesion in diverse societies is multicultural education. When it comes to ethnic content inclusion, Banks (2009) highlights that multicultural education is not only a transformative way of teaching, but an approach to empowering all the students, as it makes them critical thinkers and active citizens. It disputes the mainstream cultural values and strives to establish equity in the learning setup.

Chan et al. (2006) define social cohesion as the desire of the individuals in a society to cooperate with one another to allow survival and thrive. It is related to trust-building, the encouragement of shared values, building a sense of belonging, and affording equal opportunities. UNESCO (2017) goes further to state that social cohesion requires that societies deal with diversity, promote equality, and diffuse conflicts, which can be attained by integrative policies with education being the key tool of attaining cohesion.

The closely related theoretical strands are civic education which emphasizes on educating students on rights, responsibilities, institutions, and community participation. According to Kerr (2003), civic education can be used to secure national identity and democratic values particularly in line with the multiculturalism. The theoretical framework of the present study is, thereby, a synthesis of the concept of a multicultural education and civic development through which the potential of a curriculum in the cultivation of social cohesion is studied.

International Perspectives- Curriculum and Social Cohesion

In the world, different nations have updated their education policies and curriculum in a bid to reinforce unity and inclusivity. As an example, the national curriculum in Canada prioritizes citizenship education, cultural knowledge and rights based learning. With the help of frameworks like inclusive pedagogy and anti-racism education, Canada has developed a model, according to which students of diverse backgrounds are respected and recognized (Ghosh & Abdi, 2004).

The curriculum in the United Kingdom propagates both cultural pluralism and British values. The study of the citizenship is inculcated into other subjects such as history and religious studies in order to stimulate critical discourse on the topics of identity, democracy, and social justice (McDonough & Feinberg, 2003). Active

citizenship and equity through school-based learning was also introduced in Australian policies where the declaration referred to as "The Melbourne Declaration" was to be built.

Although Singapore is a multiethnic country, the city-state has managed to strike a balance between its national identity and the multicultural consciousness, such as that of National Education and Social Studies. They are to facilitate peace among groups of people but without losing cultural identities. The mentioned countries have suitable models which could be adopted by Pakistan in the implementation of unity, peace, and inclusivity as part of the curriculum.

Pakistan Curriculum, Identity and Textbooks

Pakistan, Curriculum has been traditionally employed in nation building, ideological control. School textbooks particularly those on Pakistan Studies have been the main vehicle in the construction of national identity, nationalist feelings and Islamic spirit. But in order to achieve this there is always a price that is paid i.e. pluralism, diversity and critical involvement.

The influential report, *The Subtle Subversion*, released by Nayyar and Salim (2003), alarmed people with systemic discriminations against religious and ethnic minorities, gender biases, and distortion of historical records. Possibly of more significance was the fact that the book *Pakistan Studies* was especially limited in its conception of identity, mostly as being a Muslim speaker of Urdu. The practices undermine students belonging to the non-dominant linguistic, ethnic, and religious groups.

As Sheikh and Gillani (2023) note, the 9th grade curriculum does not reflect the input of the minority and local cultures. Rather than creating social belonging, it upholds a precluded story. Students with diverse backgrounds find it hard to identify with themselves as equal stakeholders in the state when they are unable to perceive a national history predominant in the country as their own.

Malik (2006) too describes how the textbooks in Pakistan have always basked in military prowess and maligned other groups of the society and disregarded any sense of socio-economic inequality, creating superficial awareness of national unification. This marginalization of marginalized groups is further enhanced by the limited opportunity given to the regional histories and languages.

Single National Curriculum (SNC) and Present Changes

Pakistan initiated Single National Curriculum (SNC) in recent years aiming to make educations unaffected to the provincial variation and the variety of school systems. Even though the SNC highlights the Islamic values, sense of country, and togetherness, a wide range of scholars and civil members of the society claim that the SNC fails to be profound in inclusiveness.

According to a policy brief by the Idara-e-Taleem-o-Aagahi (2021), although the SNC has the advantage of presenting a unified approach, it has not been able to embrace progressive aspects of the inclusive narratives, gender sensitivity, and citizenship in its implementation. The SNC still prefers rote-learning and does not emphasize any critical thinking and discussion or inter-cultural dialogue.

The critics also note that instead of overcoming social rifts, the SNC actually might widens the rift between the non-Muslim communities, as well as those belonging to ethnic minorities, since the focus of the concept is that of a majority-centric identity. Also, the material does not have a connection with the contemporary topics of civic life regarding environmental responsibility, conflict resolution, human rights, and peaceful coexistence.

Inequality, Education and social Cohesion in Pakistan

It is impossible to find social cohesion without focusing on inequality. Cultural reproduction according to Bourdieu is about the inequality of access to knowledge and cultural representation that continues to create a division of classes and social isolation. There exists a stratified system of education based on classes in Pakistan public, private, and madrassah systems gathering citizens of dissimilar kinds of social capital.

The International Crisis Group (ICG, 2004) pointed out that sectarianism, extremism, and the lack of national identity based on a unified process of education are as a result of exclusive and non-standardized education. Human Rights Commission of Pakistan (HRCP) also believes that there should be a reformation of the textbooks to embrace the name of tolerance, peace and coexistence.

Moreover, the marginalization of regional dialects and culture leads to the alienation of students belonging to the province of Baluchistan, Sindh and Gilgit-Baltistan. This undermines the territorial and emotional unity that the curriculum aims at establishing.

Methodology

This study uses a qualitative research methodology, namely content analysis, to investigate how social cohesiveness topics are represented in the Pakistan Studies textbook for ninth graders. Finding the underlying patterns, meanings, and narratives in educational texts and evaluating textual content are two areas where qualitative content analysis excels (Krippendorff, 2004).

Published by the Federal Textbook Board, the chosen textbook is widely used in Pakistani public and private schools. Its extensive distribution and noteworthy impact on secondary school pupils' civic and national awareness led to its selection.

The study's analytical framework was modified from Forest (2000), which lists five essential social cohesiveness parameters:

Parameter A: Mutual respect and shared ideals;

Parameter B: Social order and the law;

Parameter C: Equity and unity among various groups;

Parameter D: Cooperation and trust within and across communities;

Parameter E: National identity and territorial belonging

The objective was to determine the frequency and tone of these criteria' appearance in the textbook material as well as whether or not their representation promotes or hinders social cohesion in a multicultural society such as Pakistan.

Coding Process

To guarantee thorough reading comprehension and prevent missing any implicit references, a manual line-by-line coding technique was used. Terms, phrases, situations, and images that fit into the five social cohesiveness factors were carefully analyzed in each chapter.

Three coding categories were used to each sentence or paragraph:

- **Positive** (fostering unity, inclusivity, and cohesion)
- **Neutral** (confused or informative)
- **Negative** (biased, exclusionary, and polarizing material)

Saldana's (2016) method of thematic coding, which uses several cycles of analysis to guarantee accuracy and lessen bias, served as the model for the coding process. To establish consistency in judgement, each code was examined multiple times across various text readings for dependability.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

To find patterns, the data was first coded and then arranged into frequency tables and matrices. The frequency of each parameter and its representation (positive, neutral, or negative) were summarized using descriptive statistics. This made it easier to spot prevailing narratives and any notable inconsistencies in how diversity, unity, and inclusion were portrayed.

Following the approach of quantitated content analysis, the study used basic quantification (counts, frequencies, etc.) to support thematic interpretations despite its qualitative nature (Creswell, 2014).

Trustworthiness and Validity

The study kept thorough coding logs and made sure that the decision-making process was transparently documented in order to provide credibility. Through continuous evaluation, the consistency of the coding was confirmed. Methodological rigor was attained by reflexivity and congruence with recognized frameworks, despite the fact that inter-rater reliability was not used because of the single-researcher approach.

Data Analysis

A dedicated analysis led to the conclusion that the themes concerning national identity (Parameter E) and shared values (Parameter A) are strong. But in trust-building (Parameter D) and respect to ethnic diversity, it was lowly represented.

Summary of Parameters Analysis

Textbook content mostly involved parameter A and parameter E. Parameter B (law and social order), Parameter C and D (unity, equity, trust, and cooperation) came in here and there and Parameters C and D were only briefly discussed.

The table below shows the results of content qualitative analysis. Table 1 provides the frequency with which in the textbook the parameters of social cohesion appeared. Sentiment-based classification Table 2 indicates the extent to which each of the parameters is positively or negatively described. Such concentration on national identity and shared values accompanied by the underrepresentation of trust, cooperation, and inclusion represent these tables well.

Table 1

Frequency of Social Cohesion Parameters in Textbook

Parameter	Description	Frequency in Text
A	Common values & respect	18
B	Law & order	6
C	Unity & equity	5
D	Trust & cooperation	3
E	National pride & identity	22

Table 2

Sentiment Analysis of Parameters

Parameters	Positive	Neutral	Negative
A	15	2	1
B	4	2	0
C	3	1	1
D	2	1	0
E	20	2	0

Conclusion

This paper concludes that the 9th-grade Pakistan Studies curriculum, partially achieves the objective of enhancing social cohesion. It does not pay adequate attention to diversity and intergroup cooperation although it focuses on national unity and pride. The curriculum ought to be merged with the principles of multicultural education more broadly in order to have a cohesive society.

Recommendations

1. Redesign the curriculum in a more equitable way, in ethnic and religious minorities.
2. Include the activities that encourage discussion and collaboration of multiple parties.
3. Teach teachers how to treat diversity-sensitive issues.
4. Focus on such values as empathy, tolerance, and civic responsibility.

Study Limitations

The first limitation is that this study was conducted on a specific textbook. It could have been possible to draw larger implications by addressing numerous topics or local differences in the curriculum. Moreover, the subjective approach to qualitative coding is a self-generated bias of interpretation.

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